

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH IN KARAKALPAK SCHOOLS

(in the case of grades 8-9)

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Abstract. *The scientific literature on teaching foreign languages, competency, concepts, communicative competence, and communication skills norms is covered in this article. This article's goal is to provide a definition of communicative competence and competency in this context. Furthermore, a reflection of the competency categorization has been identified.*

Keywords: *competence; competency; communicative competence; communication; criteria; createviaty; personality-individuality;*

One of the newest trends in contemporary fashion is global linguistics, which is the study of language usage strategies and competencies. Every nation's native tongue expands as it grows. Establishing an integrated learning environment facilitates the development of communicative competence, a critical ability for language development.

From the first paragraph to the end, "Supporting scientific research work on the development of the English language in our country and the tasks of international cooperation in this regard" makes evident the significance of the study conducted on the online promotion of the English language. Therefore, linguistics students should become more proficient communicators in order to establish a comprehensive learning environment based on the teacher's approach and to examine the semantic and methodological aspects of language research issues that establish the norms of cognitive, sociopragmatic, and linguistic. Due to the globalisation of language learning, open communication, and idea sharing with colleagues around the world, there is an increasing demand for language learners to enhance their English proficiency from an early age in school. Expanding the options for education-related research and information sharing is crucial in the context of globalisation. For pupils to improve their communication abilities, this is crucial.

The use of coaching to enhance the pedagogical procedures of creating a complete learning environment and to enhance students' communication abilities is given special consideration.

We argue that concepts of knowledge, competence, and competence—like goal-setting, in-depth problem-solving, thoroughness, and creative thinking—are interconnected and constitute the concepts of competence and competence. comprises qualities. The education reforms of today will only be successful if they produce highly skilled workers who will quicken the advancement of industry, research, technology, and the arts. Thus, it is imperative that every student develops distinct subject-specific abilities. In light of the modernization of secondary general education, the integration technique represents a new reality in education.

The communicative approach is understood to be predicated on the idea that learning the English language occurs naturally as a result of engaging in genuine, meaningful communication. Learners can utilise the language in the process of learning it when they are exposed to real-world conversation and engagement because it triggers them to apply their innate language learning mechanisms. Experts state that when designing exercises that guarantee communication and

interaction, the following criteria must be considered: a) communicativeness (English is learned through real-world communication and interaction); b) practicality (English is learned through the process of completing a specific task); and c) comprehensibility and meaningfulness (English is learned when it is understandable and meaningful to the student).[6:354]. It is not appropriate for one interviewee to know what information the other possesses or knows. In other words, "What day of the week is today?" is asked even if it is known what day of the week it is. There will be no contact if "Friday" is the response to the query. Because one of the interviewees has the chance to learn fresh facts that he was unaware of. The fact that the student must provide an official response to such queries in order to receive a grade pleases him. Consequently, motivation wanes.

The dialogue's participants should decide for themselves when, how, and to whom to say what. That is, the student's speech should not be subject to the teacher's rigid supervision over its form and substance. Reacting to the addressee's response is essential for contact and communication to take place. That is, the speaker need to elicit a response of some sort from the audience and ensure that he presents his viewpoint in a comprehensible manner.

On teaching foreign languages S.Yu. Godunova (language development), L.K. Salnaya (vocational orientation to foreign language communication), O.N. Fedorova (teaching English in the competence approach), N.A. Gazova (professional competence of specialists in the English language formation), I.R. Agasieva (informative reading of special texts teach), V.V. Bondareva (foreign language for non-philological faculty students teaching written speech), T.N. Sukhareva (word based on English language materials formation of communicative strategies in use), E.P. Shchoseva (1-formation of monologic speech in English in stage students), M.H. Karakhodzhaeva (professional speech of non-philological group students method of formation based on the verb), N. V. Zemlyanskaya (oral speech degree), S.A. Gadjieva (grammatical aspects of oral speech) [7:3].

Competence is knowledge in one or another field [4:196].

"Competence" (lat. *competo* - I am achieving, I am worthy, I am worthy) - 1) a specific state body (local self-government body) or official powers of a person defined by law, charter or other document, scope of rights and duties; 2) knowledge, experience in one or another field [5:704]. 16 different meanings of the word competence are given by psychologists in 7 different ways used a rating scale (internet-association of psychologists expert).

The concepts mentioned by the experts are as follows:

- the ability to solve production issues;
- ability to apply knowledge and skills in specific situations;
- compliance with the description of the professional standard;
- formation of quality activity of the subject by the organization the requirement placed on the worker in order to;
- compatibility of the employee's behavioral norms with the organization;
- knowledge, skills and competences (KSC), ability, motivation, personality, a general set of communicative qualities and other concepts;
- quality work training and skills;
- responsibility and authority for job duties;
- KSC+ important professional qualities;
- various aspects of competence;

- important professional qualities together with the organizational context;
- deep understanding of professional experience;
- personality, individuality;
- human factor in successful activity;
- criteria of effective production activity;
- creativity;
- production tasks in specific organizations. [7:4]

As a result, competence is knowledge, skills, abilities, reason factors, personal qualities, general harmony of target situations which is a specific organization, specific group, specific workplace, specific employee provides effective solutions for release team executives.

The concept of competence refers to the ability of a student in a particular field (e.g. competence acquired by the future teacher), that is, a certain a fully formed set of qualities is understood [1:55]. Competence concept (derived from the Latin word *competentia*, compete — "together we will achieve, we will win, we will match, we will be right". means) and in dictionaries "a way to think about something to have the knowledge to give", "to be informed, to be entitled". means Practically all dictionary compilers use "competence" and limits the categories of "competence". Definition of competence similar and replace (complement) each other at the same time [7:5].

There is no single interpretation for the word competence, this concept is "a set of powers (rights and obligations) the law of some body or official, this body or other circumstances prescribed by the regulations". "having knowledge that allows one to think about something (possess)', 'a set of questions (area) that someone is well versed in' understood [3:209].

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